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Multi-actor Network to Boost Short Food Supply Chains Across Europe

Welcome to the latest edition of the
EU4Advice Newsletter!

Introducing the EU4Advice Video!

skills of those involved in **Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs)**, which connect farmers directly with consumers.

[Watch it here](#)

Patricia Mora, EU4Advice Coordinator

In this video, **Patricia Mora McGinity**, coordinator of EU4Advice, shares key insights into this project aimed at strengthening Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) across Europe. Learn about the project's goals, expected impacts, and achievements, as well as the role of national Living Labs in fostering innovation and collaboration.

[Watch it here](#)

EU4Advice Past Events

EU4Advice has organized and participated in events on Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), Living Labs, rural women, sustainable food in smart cities, peer-learning, and AKIS.

Updates, briefings, and facilitated discussions on transforming food systems across the island of Ireland.

FEEDING OURSELVES AUTUMN ON-LINE GATHERING

Thursday, 24 October 2024

“Feeding Ourselves” Online Gathering

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Supporting Local Food Systems and Innovation in the BIOEAST Countries

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U4Advice Joins Discussions at Dutch AKIS

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CLEVERFOOD Peer-Learning Programme

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More Past & Upcoming EU4Advice Events

Articles

Please find here a set of articles developed within the EU4Advice project. These articles explore key topics related to advisory services, policy development, and knowledge-sharing across Europe.

Celebrating Two Years of EU4ADVICE: Achievements and Future Directions

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Addressing Gender Inequality in Agriculture: A Key Focus of EU4Advice

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mapping SFSC advisors in Europe

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Advisors' section

Join the first-ever European advisory network focused on short food supply chains (SFSCs)

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Sister Project: COREnet News

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